
BIOLOGICAL TEACHERS' JOB PERFORMANCE BASED ON LEADERSHIP AND TRUST

Vina Rahmadiana ^{*1}, I Made Putrawan ², Mieke Miarsyah ³

^{*1, 2, 3} Biological Education Department, Universitas Negeri Jakarta, Indonesia

Abstract:

The purpose of this study research is to know effect of leadership and trust in teacher performance in Public High Schools in DKI Jakarta. This research was conducted using survey methods with quantitative approaches and path analysis techniques (path analysis). The population of this study was 111 teachers. Research sample selected as many as 91 teachers using the simple random sampling technique. The data were obtained through questionnaires and analyzed using path techniques. Based on the results of data analysis in the research wet can be concluded: first, teacher leadership has a direct effect on significant performance. Second, trust has a direct effect on significant performance. Third, teacher leadership has a direct effect on significant trust. Fourth, teacher leadership has a direct effect on performance through teachers leadership and trust.

Keywords: Job Performance; Teachers Leadership; Trust; Path Analysis.

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1. Introduction

The research about the influence of transformational leadership and trust in teacher organizational commitment in State High Schools in DKI Jakarta is very important role in the development of education science. The teacher is a very important spearhead to determine the overall educational system. Thus, to be able to improve the quality of education, teachers needed by schools are teachers who are professional, qualified, behave well and are highly committed to school. It can be interpreted that the improvement in the quality of education starts with the teacher. Since the teacher is a determinant of the success of education, efforts to improve the quality of education must start from the aspect of the teacher. It is difficult to expect an increase in the quality of education if it does not reflect the improvement in the teachers quality [12].

Teachers that professional are located as agents of learning with the purpose of improving the quality of education, in this case teachers must have good competence. If the teachers competency is very good, then the teacher's performance in the learning process is also very good resulting in quality education [16]. Teacher performance must be improved given the challenges of education to produce quality human resources that compete in the increasingly tight globalization era [14].

In order to improve the performance of teachers, many are related to various things, such as leadership, trust, organizational culture, job satisfaction. One of them is teacher leadership, because the leadership model that leads to the achievement of the teaching and learning process so that the teacher will show good attitudes or behavior in improving performance. Besides the influence of teacher leadership there is also the influence of trust. Trust is a belief in one's integrity, ability or character. High trust can encourage performance in the teacher [1].

Colquitt and his colleagues stated that Performance is the value of a set of employee behaviors that contribute both positively and negatively to organizational fulfillment. There are three factors that influence performance according to Colquitt and colleagues, namely: (1) task performance, (2) citizenship behavior, (3) counter productive behavior [11].

Robbins and Timothy A. Judge stated that task performance is an effort in carrying out tasks and responsibilities that contribute to the production of goods or services or for administrative tasks. Schermerhorn explained that performance is measured as the quantity and quality of tasks conducted both by individually and in groups [21].

The performance is a product produced by an employee in a unit of time determined by certain criteria. The product can be in the form of goods and services. The specified time unit can be one to five years or more. Criteria are determined by the requirements set by the authorities. To measure job performance, the most important problem is to set criteria or standards. If the criteria have been determined, the next step is to collect information relating to this for a certain period. By comparing the results to the standards made for the period of time concerned, a person performance level will be obtained [23].

Teacher leadership is the same as other forms of leadership, namely the process of influencing others, in this case teacher leadership aims to improve student learning through the learning process [2]. In the practice, the teacher leadership involves various teacher activities such as developing a shared teacher's vision; managing organizational teacher programs through curriculum planning and programs, monitoring student learning and teaching; promote professional learning and uphold academic standards [20].

According to Bass & Riggio that leadership moves from Laissez-Faire, management by exception (passive), management by exception (active), contingent rewards, individualized consideration, intellectual stimulation, inspirational motivation, hingga idealized influence that more close to idealized influence more better the leadership is. Leadership from Laissez-Faire until contingent rewards is transactional, whereas from individualized to idealized influence is transformational [5].

Reinhartz & Beach [7] in Husaini Usman stated that the way to build trust is a leader who is able to adapt; firm in its stance; care; and can be trusted (honest); together creating vision and culture; together creating value by achieving goals; become a good listener; demonstrating professional skills; commitment to yourself, groups and organizations [23]. Alifiulah Utaminingsih, stated that trust is an important element that encourages the effectiveness of cooperation and communication in the proper functioning of the organization [3].

Fred Luthans stated that trusts were not only built between one employee and another employee. Trust is an important and important thing in an institution that is said to be professional. This means something that is said to be professional in carrying out a work implied by a trust [13].

This research try to find out how to fill gaps that have not been investigated in previous studies by focusing on the positive correlation of performance leadership, a positive correlation to trust in performance and a positive correlation of leadership to trust.

2. Materials and Methods

This study was a quantitative research, a causal associative type with survey method. Its data were analyzed through path analysis. Meanwhile, the population in this study were State Senior High School Teachers (SMA) in DKI Jakarta, with the number of teachers amounted to 111. Based on the McClave formulae, the researchers took 91 respondents. Additionally, the data collection technique in this study was done by using questionnaire containing several questions. The list of questions distributed must be fulfilled by the respondent to get information about the influence of teacher leadership (X1), and trust (X2) on performance (X3).

After the data was collected, it was analyzed through descriptive statistics to describe the condition of each variable by looking at the lowest score, highest score, average, median, mode, standard deviation, variance, frequency distribution, and presenting it in the histogram.

Next, the researchers conducted prerequisite tests in the form of normality using Kolmogorov-Smirnov, significance tests, and linearity regression. Finally, the hypothesis test is carried out by testing the path of the research hypothesis using the path analysis method. Then, the hypothesis of testing uses a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$.

3. Results and Discussions

The data in this study are primary data. It was obtained from the questionnaire filled by 91 respondents who have purpose to measure three variables, that are teacher leadership, trust, and performance. In this research, normality testing should use the Komolgorov-Smirnov test, so in this opportunity testing the difference in normality between estimated errors $X_3 - (\hat{X})^3$ through model $(\hat{X})^3 = 23,725 + 0,353 X_1$, and the estimated difference in error $X_2 - (\hat{X})^2$ through model $(\hat{X})^2 = 32,566 + 0,135 X_2$, and the estimated difference $X_1 - (\hat{X})^1$ through model $(\hat{X})^1 = 70,939 + 1,018 X_1$ assumed to be normal.

Next, for the results of homogeneity tests on exogenous variables with endogenous variables forming the groups that should be and with the endogenous group this group is the same variance using the Bartlett Test which is assumed to be homogeneous.

Table 1: ANAVA Table for Regression Model of $(\hat{X})^3 = 23,725 + 0,353 X_1$

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t _{hitung}	t _{tabel}	Correlations		
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Zero-order	Partial	Part
1 (Constant)	23,725	3,691		6,428				

X1	0,353	0,043	0,656	8,193*	1,986	0,656	0,656	0,656
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*: p < 0,05

Table 2: ANAVA Table for Regression Model of $(\hat{X})^3 = 32,566 + 0,135 X_2$

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t _{hitung}	t _{tabel}	Correlations		
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Zero-order	Partial	Part
1 (Constant)	32,566	4,636		7,025				
X2	0,135	0,029	0,439	4,607*	1,986	0,439	0,439	0,439

*: p < 0,05

Table 3: ANAVA Table for Regression Model of $(\hat{X})^2 = 70,939 + 1,018 X_1$

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t _{hitung}	t _{tabel}	Correlations		
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Zero-order	Partial	Part
1 (Constant)	70,939	12,940		5,482				
X1	1,018	0,151	0,581	6,732*	1,986	0,581	0,581	0,581

*: p < 0,05

The next step after testing the significance and linearity of the regression equation is path analysis test. Based on Table 1, Table 2, and Table 3, the empirical model of the results of the path analysis test can be seen in Figure 1

The hypothesis testing in this research is conducted to explain the direct influence of teacher leadership on the performance, trust in performance, and teacher leadership on trust using path analysis.

Table 4: A Summary of Hypothesis Test's Results

Direct or Indirect	n	Path Coefficient	t _{hitung}	t-table	
				0,05	0,01
X ₁ on X ₃	91	0,656	8,193**	1,9866	2,6315
X ₂ on X ₃	91	0,439	4,607**	1,9866	2,6315
X ₁ on X ₂	91	0,581	6,732**	1,9866	2,6315
X ₁ on X ₃ through X ₂	91	0,256	7,656**	1,9869	2,6322

This research results indicate that (1) leadership has a significant direct effect on performance with the Phi31 path coefficient = 0.656 and t_{cal} = 8.193; (2) trust significant direct effect on performance with the Phi32 path coefficient = 0.493 and t_{cal} = 4.607; (3) leadership has a

significant direct effect on trust with the Phi21 path coefficient = 0.581 and $t_{cal} = 6.732$; and (4) leadership has a significant direct effect on performance through trusts with the Phi31.2 path coefficient = 0.256 and $t_{cal} = 7.656$. The summary of the results of the hypothesis test is presented in Table 4.

From the testing results of the first hypothesis shows that there is a positive direct effect of leadership on performance. Based on the results of the study, the higher the leadership, the higher the performance of the teacher. Leadership has positive values to always provide positive energy so that it can influence the teacher to have high performance. The results of this study are in line with the opinions of several experts including Yukl (2010) that leadership has implications for performance orientation. Of the several types of leadership behavior relevant to improving performance and efficiency [24].

Robbin also explained that leadership has a relationship that is consistent with group performance. Robbin explains Behavior shown by a leader has a relationship that is consistent with group performance. From this explanation it can be drawn an understanding that leadership influences performance [22].

Based on Langton and Robbins's opinion, it can be explained that the four most significant factors related to teacher group performance are adequate resources, effective principal leadership, climate of trust, performance evaluation and reward systems that reflect group contributions [22].

The second hypothesis testing results show that there is a significant influence between trusts and performance. Based on the results of these studies, the higher the trust, the higher the performance of the teacher. Trust is a factor that can affect the teacher to have high performance.

Thus, it is proven that trust can influence the performance. This is in accordance with R.C's theory. Mayer, Davis, J.H., and Shoorman, F.D who stated that one of the factors that affect trust is ability, while performance is also formed by one of the important components which is ability [21].

Performance and trust have a causal relation, in terms of giving influence between one variable and another. Positive performance makes trusts positive and vice versa negative performance will have an impact on trusts which also become negative as well [14].

If the performance is measured by a person ability or potential inherent in individuals or groups, then the trust arises because of the ability or potential possessed by the individual or group. So performance is generated because of the inherent attributes of individuals or groups which ultimately lead to trust [19].

The testing results of the the third hypothesis indicate that there is a significant direct influence between teacher leadership on trust, so it is evident that leadership can influence trust. When a teacher has a high leadership value then the teacher directly has high trust too. This is in accordance with the opinion of some experts including Robbins and Judge stating that Trust is the main attribute associated with leadership. If it is not trusted it will have a serious effect on group performance. To be trusted we must be honest, faithful in supporting others, keep believing in ourselves and do what we should do [22].

Trust is the main attribute associated with leadership. If it is not trusted it will have a serious influence to the group performance [17]. The task part of the leader is to work together with other people and continually seek creative ideas and solutions to find solutions to problems faced by the teacher in the learning process in school, a leader who has full access to knowledge and creative thinking but their use in solving problems depends on the level of trust of many people towards the leader. To be trusted we must be honest, faithful in supporting others, keep believing in ourselves and do what we should do [18].

The fourth test results show that there is a significant indirect influence between leadership on performance through trust, so that it can be said that trust is a good intervening variable between leadership and performance. Chia-Nan Chiu explained that evidence from the literature shows that trust can play an intermediary role in sharing, acquiring, and transferring knowledge. Therefore, this study extends the literature and existing efforts to examine the role of mediating trust between the ability of process knowledge and the ability of knowledge infrastructure and organizational performance [9].

Cho and Ringquist found a positive correlation between trust and leadership and performance, this study revealed that the level of individual trust is expected to have some effect on the performance they can show. This means that trust will emerge in the leadership style, giving rise to performance and therefore trust as mediation [10].

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on these results, it can be concluded "If the performance of Biology teachers in relation to their ability to manage the class as long as PBM so that the performance of Biology teachers becomes more uniform in minimizing the variations in Biology teacher performance, then factors such as teacher leadership and trust are considered empowered, especially in its influence on the performance of biology teachers. "

Based on the results of the research and discussion above, the following suggestions can be considered: (1) School Supervisors supervise / supervise the implementation of High School Education in DKI Jakarta to achieve effective and efficient school goals. (2) For Principals Strive to create teacher performance in the school environment through supervision, leadership or creating a good work culture. (3) Teachers improve performance by trying to improve their teaching skills so that the attitude of the leader is created and honest, consistent in order to be trusted.

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*Corresponding author.

E-mail address: vinarahmadiana17@ gmail.com